

PREDICTION OF FIBER ORIENTATION IN COMPLEX INJECTION MOLDED PARTS

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ABSTRACT

A method is presented for simulating the evolution of a suspension of fibers during the filling of thin injection molded parts. As the behaviour of the suspension is strongly dependent on fiber length, a different model is used for short or long fibers. In the latter case, we suppose that a plug flow holds in the cavity, and orientation of the fibers is assumed to be parallel to the midsurface, while, in the former case, fiber orientation is arbitrary and the velocity profile is no longer flat.

The orientation field is predicted on the basis of a constitutive equation for the second order orientation tensor (Advani & Tucker 1990). Flow calculation is decoupled from orientation prediction (Henry de Frahan & al. 1992, Verleye and Dupret 1992). The influences of fountain flow, abrupt changes of thickness, or bifurcations of the midsurface are taken into account in the model.

The problem is fully transient and is solved on the time dependent flow domain. Approximate equations are obtained by using the Galerkin finite element method. Several examples are analysed.

1. INTRODUCTION

In most applications of injection molding, mold design remains largely based on experience. This includes, in particular, the selection of the gate and runners feeding system. In the case of fiber-reinforced suspensions, the anisotropic mechanical properties of the cooled part (which are expected to result in structural reinforcements) are directly related to the orientation field which prevails at the end of the filling and packing stages. The location of the gates has a very strong influence on the final orientation of the fibers. Therefore, designing a suitable feeding system requires a long and costly tuning of the apparatus, unless the predictive capability of modern computers is used.

Developing an accurate model for predicting fiber orientation in injection molding is however a very complex problem, since several physical mechanisms must be taken into account, which are not yet completely understood. In practical situations, the interaction between the fibers and their influence on the flow rheology are generally non-negligible. Moreover, injection molded parts are usually thin, which means that fibers do not move freely and interact with the walls of the cavity, especially at the flow front. In general, taking account of fiber-fiber, fiber-flow, and fiber-wall interactions represents a succession of modelling problems of increasing difficulty. An efficient way to describe the random and anisotropic distribution of the fibers in the fluid is to introduce orientation tensors (Advani and Tucker 1987, 1990). This approach allows one to easily develop models taking the fiber-fiber interaction into account (which is significant in a non-dilute suspension). On the other hand, the coupling of flow and orientation calculations has been addressed in the case of a dilute suspension only (Dinh and Armstrong 1984, Lipscomb and Denn 1988). These investigations have shown that coupled orientation-flow problems are very difficult to solve. The interaction between the fibers and the walls of the mold has not yet been addressed in literature.

In the sequel, two problems will be investigated. In the first case, we will consider a dilute suspension of very short fibers. Here, all the interactions are neglected, but a main difficulty is to model the effect of fountain flow on the distribution of the fibers. The orientation field is three-dimensional and time dependent, and is not parallel to the midsurface of the cavity. Flow calculations are non-isothermal, and the fluid is assumed to be generalized Newtonian, with a power-law dependence of the viscosity with respect to shear rate, and an exponential dependence with respect to temperature. In the second case, we consider a concentrated suspension of long fibers. We assume that the important fiber-fiber interaction induces a plug flow, and that fiber-fluid interaction results in an equivalent Newtonian flow behavior, where the viscosity is function of the material properties of the solvent, and the length, concentration and mechanical properties of the fibers. The fiber-wall interaction is so important that fibers cannot rotate in the gapwise direction, and remain thus parallel to the midsurface. Calculations are isothermal. We introduce a new model for taking into account the influence of an abrupt change of thickness or a bifurcation of the midsurface on the orientation field.

2. GOVERNING EQUATIONS AND NUMERICAL METHOD

In order to perform decoupled non-isothermal flow calculations, we follow the method of Dupret and Vanderschuren (1988), Couniot et al. (1989, 1993), and Dupret and Dheur (1992). The midsurface of the cavity is supposed to be composed of a set of planar facets, each being of continuous thickness $2h$. Assuming Hele-Shaw approximation and constant thermal properties of the fluid, the pressure and temperature fields (p and T) are governed by the mass and energy equations,

$$\nabla_m \cdot (S \nabla_m p) = 0 \quad , \quad (1)$$

$$\rho c \frac{DT}{Dt} = k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \eta \dot{\gamma}^2 \quad , \quad (2)$$

where η , ρ , c and k denote the viscosity, specific mass, specific heat, and thermal conductivity of the fluid, while ∇_m is the gradient operator in the midsurface direction, $\frac{\partial}{\partial z}$ the derivative in the gapwise direction, and $\frac{D}{Dt}$ the material derivative; the fluidity S is a function of the viscosity material constants, the pressure gradient, and the temperature profile.

Approximate pressure and temperature fields are calculated during filling using successive finite element meshes, which are generated on the filled part of the midsurface. The method is based on selecting at the outset of the simulation a wall behaved fixed mesh which covers the whole midsurface, on recovering for each mesh generation as many elements as possible from this fixed mesh, and on using Delaunay triangulation in the generation region (Couniot 1991). Non-isothermal calculations are performed using a hybrid spatial mixed time integration scheme (Dupret and Vanderschuren 1988, Dheur 1992). A special care is devoted to taking account of the influence of fountain flow on the temperature field. Briefly, on the basis of a singular perturbation analysis (Dupret and Dheur 1992), we set apart an outer flow region, where Hele-Shaw approximation is valid, and an inner flow region (i.e., the front region), where heat diffusion and viscous heating are essentially negligible. As a consequence, the front region may be represented approximately by a set of infinitely thin straight segments perpendicular to the midsurface, within which an instantaneous advection takes place in the gapwise direction. Hence, the temperature of any material point entering the front at level z_1 and leaving it at level z_2 remains unchanged (Fig. 1). As time integration of the energy equation is Eulerian, the temperature field must be extrapolated at any time step in the region located between two successive fronts. This operation is performed by covering the inter-front region by an "extrapolation" mesh (Fig. 3), where temperatures are easily calculated from their values and gradients on the old front (Couniot et al. 1989, 1993, Dheur 1992). The fountain flow thermal boundary condition is taken into account at this stage.

Assuming a given flow rate and inlet temperature at the gate, the model is closed by introducing appropriate thermal boundary conditions on the walls, and jump conditions across any abrupt change of thickness or bifurcation of the midsurface. In the present paper, wall thermal conditions are expressed according to the approach of Dupret and Vanderschuren (1988). We identify a thermal thickness e , which is an approximate wall-coolant distance, and take into account the thermal inertia of the mold. Concerning the jump conditions across any "singular line", we use the model of Couniot et al. (1989), which is an extension of the above described fountain flow model. A schematic representation of this approximation is given in Fig. 2.

In order to define the concept of orientation tensor, we must first introduce the distribution function $\Psi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}, t)$: at any given location \mathbf{x} and time t , the probability of finding a fiber whose orientation is comprised in an infinitesimal solid angle surrounding a given orientation \mathbf{p} is

$$dP = \Psi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}, t) dp, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{p} is a unit vector and dp is an element of area on the unit sphere U . Since calculating the distribution function Ψ is too complex and unnecessary, it is essential to simplify the model. The second-order orientation tensor \mathbf{a}_2 is defined by the expression

$$\mathbf{a}_2 = \int_U \mathbf{p} \mathbf{p} \Psi dp, \quad (4)$$

and may be shown to provide an accurate way to represent the complex orientation state of the fibers in the fluid. According to Advani and Tucker (1987, 1990), the tensor \mathbf{a}_2 obeys, for slender fibers and a negligible fiber-fiber interaction, the relation

$$\frac{\delta \mathbf{a}_2}{\delta t} = -2 \mathbf{a}_4 : \mathbf{d} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{d} is the rate of strain tensor, while $\frac{\delta \mathbf{a}_2}{\delta t}$ is the upper-convected time derivative of \mathbf{a}_2 ,

$$\frac{\delta \mathbf{a}_2}{\delta t} = \frac{D \mathbf{a}_2}{Dt} - \nabla \mathbf{v}^T \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{a}_2^T \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} \quad (6)$$

and \mathbf{a}_4 is the fourth-order orientation tensor,

$$\mathbf{a}_4 = \int_U \mathbf{p} \mathbf{p} \mathbf{p} \mathbf{p} \Psi dp, \quad (7)$$

Equation (5) shows that the evolution equation for \mathbf{a}_2 involves \mathbf{a}_4 , and this means that a closure approximation is required in order to relate the evolution of \mathbf{a}_2 to the sole velocity field. In this paper, we have used the quadratic closure,

$$\mathbf{a}_4 = \mathbf{a}_2 \mathbf{a}_2. \quad (8)$$

More detail may be found in Henry de Frahan et al. (1991).

A particular difficulty is again found when considering the behavior of the suspension in the vicinity of the flow front, or of an abrupt change of thickness, or a bifurcation of the midsurface. We use a method which is based on an extension of the approach of Dupret and Vanderschuren (1988), and Couniot et al. (1993) for solving the thermal problem. Consider, for example, the case of an abrupt change of thickness, and let in Fig. 4 an elementary parallelepiped enter the singular region at a given level z_1 and leave it at level z_2 . The kinematic effects induced by the singular region may be summarized as follows:

- i. advection in the gapwise direction, from level z_1 to level z_2 ;
- ii. deformation, which consists of both shear and change of side lengths of the parallelepiped.

Our simplified model, which is described in Verleye and Dupret (1993), and Crochet et al. (1993) neglects shear deformation, which may be shown to be small, and establishes a relationship between the side lengths of the entering and outgoing elementary volumes. A similar approach is used for modelling the fountain flow. On this basis, it is possible to obtain a relationship between the ingoing and outgoing orientation tensors a_2 on both sides of the singularity.

The decoupled orientation problem is solved by means of a Galerkin finite element method which is similar to the one used for thermal calculations, but slightly more complex. Integration by part is carried out on any term involving a velocity gradient component. Detail is given in Henry de Frahan et al. (1992), Crochet et al. (1993), and Verleye and Dupret (1993).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a first problem, we analyse the non-isothermal filling of a rectangular plate. The injected fibers are assumed to be very short and slender. At the gate, the orientation is supposed to be random and parallel to the midsurface. Material data are given in Table I. The calculated temperature field and the orientation field at the end of the filling stage is represented in Fig. 5 for three different layers. It is easy to observe that a completely different behavior is exhibited in the midsurface, the intermediate layer, where shear effect is important, and the skin, where freezing influence prevails while the role of fountain flow is essential. A second problem deals with the filling of a part with a bifurcation. All the facets have the same thickness (Fig. 6). Fibers are assumed to be very long, and Newtonian isothermal calculations are performed. The strong influence of the bifurcation is obvious in Fig. 7, where a jump of orientation tensor across the bifurcation may be observed.

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Fig. 1. Fountain flow modelling

Fig. 2. Approximate model for a bifurcation of the midsurface

Fig. 3. Extrapolation mesh covering the region located between two successive fronts

Fig. 4 A simplified model for the flow in an abrupt change of thickness

$$\eta = m_0 e^{-\alpha T} \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$$

m_0	$1.44 \cdot 10^9 \text{ kg s}^{-2} \text{ m}^{-1}$	Q_{inj}	$4 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$
ρ	1200 kg/m^3	ρ_s	7800 kg/m^3
c	2200 J/kg K	c_s	460 J/kg K
k	0.215 W/m K	k_s	46 W/m K
$2h$	1 mm	e	2 mm
T_e	383 K	T_{inj}	533 K
α	0.0226 K^{-1}	n	0.665

Table 1. Material data and injection conditions

Fig. 5. Non-isothermal molding of a rectangular plate.
 Calculated temperature and orientation fields at the end of the filling
 a. $z/h = 0$; b. $z/h = 0.65$; c. $z/h = 0.99$

Fig. 6. Bifurcation of the midsurface : Branch thicknesses : 4 / 4 / 4

a. Geometry and successive flows fronts

b. Meshes

c. Fiber orientation

a.

b.

Fig. 7. Bifurcation of the midsurface : Branch thicknesses : 4 / 4 / 4

a. Geometry and cross section definition A-B

b. Fiber orientation along the cross section A-B